

Combined categories Christchurch terror attack

Condolences/support/ tributes to Muslims

14 survivor story/personal profile

15 Expressions of faith/prayers

32 Condolences to victims

33 Political solidarity

31 Community relations/cohesion

Defending Muslims

11 Pro-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [positive trait]')

12 Pro-Muslim, specific (contribution to society, acts of kindness, religion of peace, scientific endeavours etc)

13 Anti-Muslim discrimination/racism/ Islamophobia

Right wing politics

01 Anti-Muslim, general ('Muslims are [negative trait]')

02 Anti-Muslim, specific (extremism, evil, radicalisation, anti-Quran, anti-Islamic scripture etc)

03 Islamist Terrorism

04 Islamification/ spread of Islam (Cultural clash, censorship, Islam taking over the world, conversion, attacks on 'our' culture, country, Shariah law, references to the movement of refugees, Muslim problem, cultural deviance)

05 Muslims provoked Christchurch attack

06 Islamophobia is denied/exaggerated

07 white victimhood

22 Pro conservative/right agendas (not sure whether we can put this with pro white supremacy and that kind of politics!!)

- 25 Anti Labour/ left agendas / anti 'woke'
- 26 Pro-far right agenda
- 28 Pro white supremacy
- 42 Right-wing criticism of mainstream media
- 43 Tweet disseminates/premised on conspiracy theory

Global Politics/ Politics of RW terrorism

- 16 Christchurch and British politics
- 17 Christchurch and US politics
- 18 Christchurch and Indian politics
- 19 Christchurch and NZ/Australia
- 20 Christchurch & global RW extremism
- 21 Politics, general
- 30 Immigration/deportation
- 34 Causes of terrorism
- 35 Process of radicalisation
- 36 Extremism online
- 38 Gun crime/gun ownership

Left wing politics

- 23 Anti conservative/right agendas
- 24 Pro Labour/ left agendas
- 27 Anti far right agenda
- 29 Anti white supremacy
- 37 Language & reporting terrorism

41 Left-wing criticism of mainstream media

44 Tweet identifies/alleges conspiracy theory

39 Protest

45 accusation of antisemitism

46 antisemitism in content

99 Other